

Industry4Redispatch (I4RD)

Deliverable 7.2

New business models for a decarbonized and grid-supporting industry

AUTHORS

Stefan Strömer	Stefan.Strömer@ait.ac.at	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Sophie Knöttner	Sophie.Knöttner@ait.ac.at	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Simon Strehn	Simon.strehn@ait.ac.at	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Clemens Korner	Clemens.Korner@ait.ac.at	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Regina Hemm	Regina.Hemm@ait.ac.at	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Matthias Traninger	Matthias.traninger@ait.ac.at	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Sarah Fanta	Sarah.fanta@ait.ac.at	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Daniel-Leon Schultis		

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

AIT – Tara Esterl
+43 664 8157 810
Tara.esterl@ait.ac.at

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GLOSSARY

CAPEX

Capital expenditures

CBA

Cost-benefit analysis

DA

Day-Ahead

DSO

Distribution system operator

EPEX

European Power Exchange

FSP

Flexibility service provider

OPEX

Operational expenditures

RD

Redispatch

Industry4Redispatch (I4RD)

TSO

Transmission system operator

UC

Use Case

WP

Work Package

1. Executive Summary

The deliverable evaluates the integration of industrial assets into Austria's redispatch process for the year 2030. Using a detailed modelling framework and a scenario-based cost-benefit analysis (CBA), it assesses the economic and operational impacts of leveraging industrial flexibility within an increasingly renewable-centric energy system. The findings indicate that industrial participation can reduce overall congestion management costs by approximately 1 to 1.5 percent and lower curtailment of renewable electricity by up to 7.5 percent. These benefits remain evident even in scenarios with high participation markups, underscoring the robustness of the approach.

Results indicate this curtailment of renewable generation to almost triple (from 57.4 GWh during 2024, cf. [1], to around 150 GWh), reflecting the planned expansion of renewable capacity by around 11 GW—an increase by more than a third of the currently installed capacities (around 25 GW). Within this context, the participation of industrial flexibility enables a reduction of curtailment by about 7.4%, lowering the total to around 139 GWh. This reduction corresponds to roughly 20% of the observed curtailed renewable energy in 2024 and underscores the substantial potential of industrial participation in facilitating more efficient domestic utilization of renewable electricity. Even if the savings remain modest in relative terms, they make evident the potential of industrial participation to contribute to overall system efficiency, which suggests that industrial flexibility might also play a significant role in reducing the need to curtail clean energy, thereby supporting broader decarbonization and energy system transition goals.

Beyond immediate economic gains, the systemic value of industrial flexibility becomes increasingly important in a future characterized by higher renewable shares and growing grid congestion. In such a future, industrial flexibility presents a viable lever for enhancing operational efficiency and minimizing renewable energy losses. However, unlocking the full potential of these assets may require regulatory adjustments, particularly concerning the remuneration of curtailed renewable generation.

The economic viability of FSP participation in the redispatch market depends on clear regulatory frameworks, fair remuneration, and the ability to cover operational costs through at least cost-based bidding. However, uncertain activation rates and competition from other flexibility markets pose significant challenges, especially for smaller or manually operated assets.

The DSO-specific cost-benefit analysis shows that reinforcing the distribution grid increases redispatch potential and allows for more flexible bid combinations by removing grid-related limitations. This reinforcement leads to notable gains in available redispatch power, particularly during working hours, although improvements vary over time. Overall, grid reinforcement at the DSO level benefits the TSO, but must be weighed against platform and personnel costs, and its effectiveness depends heavily on network-specific conditions and future regulatory implementation.

In summary, integrating industrial flexibility into redispatch planning offers a feasible and beneficial pathway to improving decentralized support for congestion management, reducing system costs, and enabling higher renewable integration. The design of market mechanisms or regulatory frameworks that allow for cost-efficient and reliable activation of industrial assets will be crucial for realizing this potential in practice.

2. Introduction

The increasing integration of renewable energy sources and the decentralization of energy systems are fundamentally transforming power system operations across Europe. One of the critical challenges in this context is ensuring grid stability and operational security through effective redispatch mechanisms. Traditionally, redispatch has relied on large-scale conventional generators connected at the transmission network level. However, as conventional capacity diminishes and flexibility needs grow, new sources of redispatch potential must be explored.

Industrial facilities, particularly those connected at distribution network levels, represent a largely untapped source of flexibility. The Industry4Redispatch (I4RD) project explored how industrial consumers and prosumers can contribute to redispatch by providing both demand- and supply-side flexibility. To support this, the project assessed the flexibility potential within Austria, quantifying its magnitude, geographical distribution, resource types, and directional capability (i.e., increasing or decreasing consumption or generation). These findings formed a critical

input to a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis (CBA), both from TSO and from industry perspective. The results are presented in this Deliverable, where scenarios with and without industrial participation in redispatch are compared. A European transmission system model reflecting projected grid conditions for the year 2030 was used to simulate redispatch activations under realistic generation and load scenarios, taking into account cross-border power flows, network constraints, and regional flexibility availability. This model is described in Deliverable D7.3.

The aim of the conducted CBA is on determining individual costs and benefits for providers of redispatch as well as the costs for the TSO with and without industrial participation, as well as for the DSO comparing the situation with grid reinforcement vs. using the bid filter. The methodology applied in this analysis was developed collaboratively with stakeholders and is comprehensively described in Deliverable 7.1. This current deliverable builds on that foundation by presenting the resulting findings and evaluating the implications of industrial involvement in redispatch for both TSOs, industrial actors, flexibility service providers as well as DSOs.

3. TSO perspective

This section presents the results from the CBA from TSO perspective, as described in Deliverable D7.1. The baseline scenario assumes that the TSO manages redispatch solely through conventional power plants, while industrial consumers participate exclusively in the day-ahead electricity market without engaging in redispatch mechanisms. To assess the potential benefits of increased flexibility, this baseline scenario is compared to an alternative case in which industrial consumers actively participate in a potential redispatch market. The analysis aims to quantify the overall economic impact of integrating industrial flexibility into redispatch processes from TSO as well as from industries perspective. The scenarios also explore different pricing schemes, including varying markup levels applied either uniformly across all providers or specifically to industrial participants.

3.1. Assumptions

The decision to conduct the CBA based on the one exemplary year 2030 rather than using long-term evaluation methods, such as NPV, was driven by the need for a practical and realistic, near-term assessment. Long-term projections are inherently uncertain due to factors such as evolving regulatory frameworks, technological advancements, market dynamics, grid conditions, pricing mechanisms and changes in industrial participation. While suffering from uncertainties, selecting one representative year can showcase the effect of various external factors in an intuitive way that can be reproduced and used to study for example extreme events like dark doldrums ensuring a reliable and relevant analysis.

To quantify the influence of industry participating in the redispatch process, the previously determined available flexibility potential per industry sector is used. Typical bid patterns as well as load profiles per industry sector were already derived in the project (see Deliverable D7.3). These industry bids were geographically distributed in the Austrian electricity network according to available statistical data and additional available information about the location of large industrial plants.

The baseline scenario, the results of which are described in the following sections, is the operational status-quo, which means redispatch costs without industry participating in flexibility provision, for the year 2030. For the base scenario the redispatch demand is calculated and bids from conventional power plants are generated. With this input, a redispatch clearing algorithm is applied, resulting in activated redispatch bids and the respective costs for redispatch provision. The methods used for grid simulation and redispatch optimization are described in further detail in Deliverable D7.3.

In terms of compensation, different remuneration options have been discussed. The conclusion was that the bid costs inevitably need to cover at least the amount of actual costs for the industry's redispatch provision. Furthermore, some additional incentive for industry is required, as without any regulatory obligation, the relating effort of flexibility provision is way too high as for the industry to be profitable. Further, it could be shown that a potential market, including the additional flexibility potential of industry, does not provide enough liquidity to function optimally and must therefore be accompanied by several regulatory and coordinative measures [2]). A final

remuneration scheme will not be decided on within the project, but there are some **options which are investigated within the CBA**:

- **Same markup for all bidders:** A fixed markup is defined per MWh of energy provided for redispatch, which every bidder receives independent of their actual costs (industry sites as well as conventional plants). The costs of the total redispatch considering only conventional power plants with a specific markup of 10 EUR/MWh (see Table 1 scenario *baseline*) will be compared with the costs of total redispatch including industry and the same markup for all bidders (see Table 1 scenario *abs-10-10*). There will be an intersection, where the total costs with markup and industry will be the same as without markup and without industry. This point will define the maximum markup, suitable markups will likely lie between this markup and zero. In addition, a percentage-based markup is applied to both conventional and industrial assets for comparison purposes (see Table 1 scenario *rel-10-10*), calculated on the basis of actual cost data.
- **Markup only for industry:** A specific markup is defined per MWh of energy provided for redispatch, which all industrial/decentralized bidders receive independent of their actual costs. The assumption is, that conventional power plants are part of the grid reserve and therefore remunerated as they are used to (without markup). The markup could range from (slightly-above) zero up to a markup, where no industry plants will be activated anymore, because conventional plants are always cheaper. The real markup will likely lie again somewhere in between these two limits and is target of the investigation. A sensitivity analysis on how much of the flexibility potential is used by the TSO with which markup is carried out (see Table 1 for an overview of *abs-10-X* scenarios).

Regarding the overall design of the case-study, **additional approaches, not considered in the conducted CBA**, may present viable alternatives:

- One possibility involves remunerating redispatch bids based on a purely cost-based scheme while complementing this with targeted investment incentives provided by the TSO. In this framework, potential cost savings from redispatch provision could be evaluated against the estimated investment costs incurred by industrial participants. However, such a comparison is methodologically challenging, given the difficulty of reliably forecasting long-term redispatch revenues at specific sites. These revenues are highly sensitive to local grid constraints, geographical factors, and evolving system conditions in neighboring countries - in terms of the development of supply, demand, as well as transmission.
- Another option entails establishing a dedicated, sequential market for industrial flexibility. This would involve procuring a predefined volume of redispatch capacity from distributed flexible assets through a separate market mechanism, cleared ahead of conventional redispatch activation. Besides real-world challenges, such as the constrained time window such a process could be integrated into, considering the already existing market and system timeline until delivery, accurately modeling strategic bidding behavior in such a market would necessitate agent-based modeling, a methodological approach that lies beyond the scope of the I4RD project.

Table 1 Overview of markups for conventional and industrial assets by scenario.

Scenario	Conventional	Industrial	Notes
Baseline	+10 €/MWh	-	No industrial assets
Rel-10-10	+10%	+10%	% of the bid related operational costs
Abs-10-10	+10 €/MWh	+10 €/MWh	
Abs-10-20	+20 €/MWh	+20 €/MWh	
Abs-10-30	+30 €/MWh	+30 €/MWh	
Abs-10-40	+40 €/MWh	+40 €/MWh	
Abs-10-50	+50 €/MWh	+50 €/MWh	

Abs-10-75

+75 €/MWh

+75 €/MWh

The TSO perspective aims at reflecting the total redispatch costs from the Austrian perspective, which requires a post-processing step since the total system costs during the redispatch optimization also contain costs, e.g., induced by activated bids far from Austria. After the bid clearing process described in Deliverable 7.3, the algorithm provides the activated bids from conventional power plants as well as from industry—for this step filtered to consider Austrian assets. These costs are then compared across scenarios defined in Table 1, based on various KPIs defined in Table 2.

Table 2 Overview of KPIs defined to assess the impact of industrial participation on redispatch provision in Austria. Values are always considered to be "per one year".

KPI	Unit
Number of hours with active redispatch, across all scenarios	hour
Industrial share of total activations for redispatch, across all scenarios	%
Total system costs, across all scenarios	EUR
Reduced curtailment, across all scenarios	MWh and %
Peak activations of conventional assets, across all scenarios	MW
VWAP of flexibilities activated for redispatch, across all scenarios	EUR/MWh
Impact of industrial participation on volume share per asset type	MWh and %
Offered and accepted industrial flexibility by technology	GWh
Cumulated industrial activated flexibility by scenario	GWh

3.2. Results

Subsequently, this chapter presents the results of the eight predefined scenarios (see Table 1), emphasizing the influence of incorporating industrial assets into the redispatch mechanism. The analysis compares the baseline scenario without industrial participation to the *abs-10-10* scenario, which assumes an absolute markup of 10 €/MWh for all industrial assets. With at most around 250 MW as available industrial flexibility, the industry (without considering temporal simultaneity, etc.) is able to offer around 5% of the maximum peak requirements. Additionally, it examines the effects of varying the industrial markup from 10 €/MWh to 75 €/MWh. The discussion covers the variation in redispatch activations throughout the modelling period and across all simulation runs, highlighting differences between conventional and industrial asset activations, as well as between average and peak periods. Finally, the section analyses key performance indicators KPIs (see Table 2) defined in the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and provides detailed insights into the CBA outcomes from the Transmission System Operator's (TSO) perspective.

Figure 1 Share of industrial activations compared to the total annual volume (baseline: approximately 2.2 TWh) of necessary redispatch activations in Austria, considering the different markup scenarios defined in Table 1. With at most around 250 MW as available industrial flexibility, the industry (without considering temporal simultaneity, etc.) is able to offer around 5% of the maximum peak requirements.

With a total amount of energy activated for redispatch of approximately 2.2 TWh in the baseline scenario, it can be observed that both positive as well as negative activations are reduced when introducing industrial assets. Figure 1 shows the overall share of energy provided by industrial assets, across all scenarios. Starting at roughly 30 GWh annually of both positive and negative activations, increasing the markup continuously decreases the industrial share. This affects positive activations (down to 8 GWh) considerably more than negative ones (down to 16 GWh) in scenario 10-75.

The declining effect, caused by rising markups, of industrial participation observed in Figure 1 can further be analysed in Figure 2, where after an initial reduction of total system costs of roughly 1--1.5 % achieved through the integration of industrial assets (scenarios *rel-10-10* and *abs-10-10*), this positive effect quickly declines, hitting the system cost break-even point for an industrial markup of 75 EUR/MWh. However, as Figure 2 also shows, non-financial advantages may showcase a different course: A reduction by approximately 7,5% of curtailed renewable generation in Austria scenario *abs-10-10* can be achieved through the integration of industrial assets. Furthermore, the sensitivity to increasing markups is limited - with still more than 6% reduced curtailment over the baseline results for the break-even markup of 75 €/MWh.

Figure 2 Potential for the reduction of annual system costs (baseline: approx. 135 million €) caused by redispatch activations, as well as the impact of industrial participation onto the amount of curtailed renewable energy (baseline: approx. 150 GWh), in Austria, considering the different markup scenarios defined in Table 1.

Directly linked to the system costs, the last analysed financial KPI is presented in Figure 3 — the VWAP of activated positive and negative redispatch amounts. While redispatch can be seen as being remunerated in a pay-as-bid scheme, direct comparisons between bids (as well as mean or marginal prices) are of limited meaning, considering its locational properties. Nevertheless, the VWAP supports an intuitive comparison of, e.g., the markups used for the scenarios against costs caused by activations—considering the total amount of activated energy¹. It shows that positive redispatch comes at a cost roughly 30% higher than the average electricity price (at 67 EUR/MWh), with assets willing to pay back on average between 65–80% of the average electricity price (or 160–190% of the gas price). As already evident from Figure 2, integrating industrial assets shows a negligible impact for positive redispatch, whereas the VWAP for negative redispatch can be observed to drop by more than 10% initially (comparing *baseline* and *abs-10-10*), an effect that is however highly sensitive on increasing markups.

¹ Considering a simplified example with a single congestion, it is evident that since an asset can at best show a 100% sensitivity on this congestion—which will for most situations be even considerably lower than that—the change in the assets schedule will be more than the amount the line is overloaded by.

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Figure 3: Impact of industrial participation and different markup scenarios (see Table 1) onto the VWAP of flexibilities activated for redispatch in Austria. In comparison, average prices of natural gas (27 EUR/MWh), hydrogen (62 EUR/MWh), and electricity (67 EUR/MWh)—as well as other carriers—are detailed in Table 1.

A similar sensitivity can be seen when analysing the peak activations of conventional assets in Austria, see Figure 4, with almost no difference going from scenario *abs-10-10* to *abs-10-75*. However, this also shows a rather limited impact of industrial assets on the peak activations - with around 5 GW positive peaks and 2.5 GW negative peaks during times of high system stress, the industrial flexibility - all available at the same time and the necessary location(s) - is too limited to create a larger impact.

Figure 4 Impact of industrial participation and different markup scenarios (see Table 1) onto the peak capacity necessary to efficiently resolve congestions, with the baseline scenario at approx. +5.0 GW and -2.5 GW.

The slight increase in peak activations that can be observed in *rel-10-10* can be explained by the overall cost comparison to *abs-10-10*: A 10 %-markup is (sometimes considerably) cheaper than a fixed 10 €/MWh markup for wide range of assets and times; coupled with the increased flexibility offered by the industrial assets, this also entails a slight increase in conventional peak activations.

A result further supporting structural differences between positive and negative redispatch activations is given by the amount of hours that redispatch is activated in Austria, as shown in Figure 4. As evident, a more frequent utilization of flexibilities is enabled through the integration of industrial assets, with the potential of offering bids at locations or during times where none (or too inefficient) would otherwise be available in Austria. While Figure 5 highlighted that specific positive impacts achieved through the integration of industrial assets are less sensitive to high markups, the combination with Figure 5 shows that this is mostly caused by increased flexibility during times where redispatch was already activated in the baseline scenario, justified by the almost complete return to the baseline hours with active redispatch in scenario *abs-10-75*.

Figure 5 Impact of industrial participation and different markup scenarios (see Table 1) onto the number of hours annually with flexibilities in Austria being activated for redispatch. Entries show hours independent on direction ("Any"), as well as only those where positive or negative activations took place

Finally, Figure 6 gives an overview the annual shares of redispatch provided by different asset classes. The predominantly hydro-based provision of positive redispatch is caused by a scarcity of assets offering positive flexibilities in the western parts of Austria (especially Tyrol and Salzburg) and considerable flows caused by an abundance of renewable generation either to the North (Germany), causing congestions across the border, or in Eastern Europe—causing high transit flows through and consequently congestions in (central) Austria. The integration of industrial assets can be seen to mainly affect thermal- and hydro-based conventional assets, with battery storages and power-to-gas assets not being affected.

A much more considerable impact can be seen comparing the share of negative volumes in Figure 6c and Figure 6d, where industrial assets reduce the amount of negative redispatch provided by renewables (= reduced curtailment) across all technologies. However, it can also be seen that power-to-gas assets loose around 1,5 % share - showcasing that industrial assets, as flexible demand assets, "cannibalize" other technologies in this same "pool" of assets.

Positive Redispatch

■ thermal ■ hydro ■ battery ■ power-to-gas ■ industry

(a) Positive redispatch in scenario *baseline*.

Positive Redispatch

■ thermal ■ hydro ■ battery ■ power-to-gas ■ industry

(b) Positive redispatch in scenario *abs-10-10*.

Negative Redispatch

■ thermal ■ hydro ■ battery ■ power-to-gas ■ industry ■ pv ■ wind ■ run-of-river

(c) Negative redispatch in scenario *baseline*.

Negative Redispatch

■ thermal ■ hydro ■ battery ■ power-to-gas ■ industry ■ pv ■ wind ■ run-of-river

(d) Negative redispatch in scenario *abs-10-10*.

Figure 6 Share of different asset types on the total activated volume across Austria, comparing positive ((a) & (b)) and negative ((c) & (d)) redispatch, as well as without (scenario baseline in (a) & (c)) against with (scenario *abs-10-10* in (b) & (d)) industrial participation. Total annual volumes in baseline at approx. 1,8 TWh of positive and 0,4 TWh of negative activated volume.

The model's redispatch cost estimates at 135 million EUR/year indicate a similar magnitude to historical data (85-140 million EUR/year, cf. [3]), which however do not consider activations for Germany in Austria but on the other hand do consider grid reserve), lending credibility to the simulation results. Results show a total of 2.2 TWh of (positive and negative) activations for the provision of redispatch, corresponding to around 2.5 % of the annual demand of 90 TWh — again in comparison to recent redispatch demands in the 1-3 TWh range between 2018 and 2024.

Potential future increases of activated redispatch may, besides rising costs or increased CO₂ emissions, also increase the curtailment of renewable generation for redispatch — which is clearly not desirable. As stated by APG, this already resulted in a "loss" of national renewable generation amounting to around 57.4~GWh during 2024 (cf. [1]). In this context of curtailment, a specific model assumption has to be discussed: As results shown in Figure 6 indicate, curtailment of solar photovoltaic assets contributes a considerable amount to the overall needed negative flexibility

— almost half the industrial assets' final share of the total volume is linked to a reduction solar photovoltaic curtailment. However, this model result would currently not be observable in reality, as many of these assets currently benefit from contracted fixed feed-in tariffs — many of which will remain in place for several more years — or from market premiums. These premiums are typically adjusted based on the average monthly market value. A suspension of it only takes place if market prices are negative for a continuous period of six hours. Generally, such premiums are only paid if the asset actually generates electricity during the specified delivery period. Curtailment of such an asset, caused by the provision of negative redispatch, would therefore incur opportunity costs in the same extent — essentially rendering these flexibilities too costly to activate. Creating an exception to this regulation for generation schedules that were modified due to a redispatch activation, would circumvent this issue and considerably increase the amount of negative flexibility.

4. Industry perspective

In the following, a closer analysis of the industrial contribution is performed. Figure 7 shows the location of identified sites fulfilling the requirement of providing positive and/or negative flexibility with at least 1 MW. With at most around 250 MW (based on the assumption above including only sites with flexibility of at least 1 MW) as available industrial flexibility, the industry (without considering temporal simultaneity, etc.) is able to offer around 5% of the maximum peak requirements.

Figure 7 Localization of identified industrial sites attractive for flexibility provision in Austria.

Based on the applied filtering criteria a total of 23 sites was identified, whereas some of them can offer flexibility with multiple assets. In Eastern Austria, several assets were identified providing negative or negative and positive flexibility. In Western Austria, comparably more assets can be found providing only positive flexibility.

Figure 8 shows how the offered flexibility and the activated flexibility in different scenarios differ, especially technology-wise. Especially, the offered flexibility is dominated by negative flexibility, which can be explained by the assumption made for this work, that especially typical energy supply units such as steam turbines, gas turbines or different CHP plants are operated close to full load.

Regarding the activation, one can see that with low markups (10 EUR/MWh), especially the activated negative flexibility is significantly lower than the offered flexibility (see Figure 8). Also, for positive bids, the energy of the overall accepted bids is significantly smaller than the amount offered. Increasing the markup up to 75 EUR/MWh

Figure 8 Overview of offered and accepted positive and negative flexibility per technology for different markups.

(a) Offered, aggregated industrial flexibility per technology for all scenarios.

(b) Accepted, aggregated industrial flexibility per technology for 10 EUR/MWh markup.

(c) Accepted, aggregated industrial flexibility per technology for 75 EUR/MWh markup.

further lowers the accepted amount—here, no clear trend can be identified technology-wise. This leads to the conclusion that the specific location of the technology is of high relevance for the activation.

It shall be noted that following limitations can be identified for the methodological approach to identify industrial flexibility in this study. First, the bids were derived from a technology base currently (2025) in place. No significant technology transition pathways have been considered. Second, due to a defined minimum bid size of 1~MW it was implicitly assumed, that only "large" sites would offer bids. However, in the presented use case all the remaining sites participated in the assumed redispatch market. It would probably not be possible to exploit the full potential due to restrictions at the locations, alternative, possibly more attractive markets, etc.

It was proceeded on the assumption that all participating locations meet the technical and organizational requirements for participation in the market. Some but not all companies are currently able to participate in this or other flexibility markets.

5. Flexibility service provider (FSP) perspective

To better understand the practical implications and stakeholder-specific interpretations of the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) results, the I4RD project gathered and reflected on the perspectives of involved Flexibility Service Providers (FSPs). The guiding questions that shaped this exchange were originally developed in Deliverable 7.1 as part of the project's overarching methodological framework. The following section summarizes the key viewpoints from the FSPs regarding the feasibility of industrial participation, business model viability, aggregation strategies, and operational barriers, as revealed by the CBA results.

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From the perspective of Flexibility Service Providers, are total markups in the range of €10–75/MWh, as discussed in the paper, sufficient to cover their costs, in case that their costs cannot be integrated into the cost-based component of their bids?

Regarding whether total markups in the range of €10–75/MWh are sufficient to cover the costs for an FSP, the general consensus highlights several important considerations. For example, a small virtual power plant (VPP) consisting of 10 hydropower units of 100 kW each, offering 1 MWh per day, would generate an annual revenue of approximately €27.375 at €75/MWh. However, this revenue must be shared among all units, which makes the business case only moderately attractive. Furthermore, the sufficiency of the markup depends heavily on factors such as the probability of activation and operational costs per activation, which vary based on the specific market framework and the technical setup of the assets. Manual efforts are required to process bids or operate small plants (<1 MW), therefore including FSP operational expenses in the cost-based bid component is essential. While assets already participating in other flexibility markets may require lower additional effort and thus fit better into this remuneration range, enabling previously unused flexibility would likely require higher markups than the proposed ones, to create sufficient incentives.

Are there enough bids available for aggregation to reach the minimum bid size within one allowed aggregation area (on 110kV Level)?

According to feedback from the FSPs, it is expected that at this aggregation level, assembling at least 1 MW is feasible.

By combining which assets does the FSP reach the minimum bid size?

It is envisioned that multiple smaller assets, such as several 100 kW hydropower plants, can be aggregated to reach the minimum bid size. Ideally, bids should be structured in whole megawatt increments, since this also aligns with minimum bid requirements of other markets. Aggregation is preferably done among assets with similar cost structures, though the exact mix may vary daily depending on the specific markets in which the assets participate and their relative attractiveness.

Which individual costs do the single assets have, are their costs quite similar? Is the distribution of costs in one potential aggregated bid rather wide or very narrow?

The costs are expected to vary significantly between assets. Even among plants dedicated solely to energy provision, large differences in cost structures are likely—for example, when comparing power-to-heat units, gas turbines, or photovoltaic installations with market price premiums. Therefore, the cost distribution within an aggregated bid may be quite wide.

Will the FSP be able to provide any kind of forecast which changes the bidding behaviour of single plants and therefore the aggregation possibilities?

It is considered essential for FSPs to offer clear, location-specific guidance on suitable bidding windows to facilitate effective aggregation of smaller bids. Ideally, bidding opportunities would cover all timeframes but be supported by transparent recommendations on when to target bids. However, forecasting the attractiveness of this particular market and the probability of activation is challenging, especially since the market is not yet established. The less predictable these factors are, the less attractive the market becomes for providers, potentially making it a last-resort option for utilizing flexibility not engaged elsewhere.

If sufficient assets are available, what aggregation strategy might Flexibility Service Providers adopt? It could be e.g. to mix cheap and expensive bids for aggregation, aggregate only bids with similar prices, etc.

The aggregation strategy will largely depend on the specific goals and constraints of each FSP, as well as on the experience gathered with the market over time. Aggregating assets with similar cost structures tends to ensure fairer treatment of individual providers, as mixing cheaper and more expensive bids can disadvantage the cheaper assets

by lowering their activation chances in the merit order. Conversely, combining bids with varied costs could increase the total activated volume. The exact approach is highly individual and may even be considered proprietary.

A common view is that, to avoid competition conflicts among providers, aggregation should preferably group assets with similar costs when there are enough assets available. A more detailed strategy will likely emerge with further market experience and clarity. For a cost-based market with markups, aggregating similarly priced assets appears most efficient, aligning closely with the optimum dispatch of individual assets. However, if the market operates as pay-as-bid, aggregation strategies would differ accordingly, also influenced by how assets participate in other flexibility markets.

How are the plants located within and in between the 110 kV grids? Some areas could be more useful for aggregation than others, but there is only a limited amount of information about the distribution grids available.

The suitability of business models, also depends on other currently available business and marketing models, such as the provision of balancing reserve. How are the current business models for balancing reserve currently structured? Are providers typically paid via a flat-rate fee for marketing their full capacity, remunerated per marketed megawatt of accepted capacity or energy, or compensated through a percentage of the actual revenues achieved?

From the perspective of small Virtual Power Plants (VPPs), it was emphasized that if flexibility is more profitable when used for balancing group settlement (to avoid imbalance), it is unlikely to be offered for redispatch. Market participants confirmed that all common remuneration models—flat-rate fees, payments per marketed capacity/energy, or revenue sharing—are present in the market. However, due to strategic reasons, specific contractual arrangements chosen by providers could not be disclosed.

How do the probabilities of activation for redispatch change the business case?

Regarding the impact of activation probabilities on the business case, one viewpoint referenced the earlier discussion on markups, noting that if activation occurs only about 33% of the time, the annual revenue for the FSP and assets drops to roughly €9,000, significantly worsening the business case. Another emphasized that this uncertainty is a key challenge in cost-based models with markups — the greater the uncertainty around activation, the lower the incentive for asset owners to make initial investments.

Will there be several active FSPs participating? This would again have impact on liquidity, cost distribution etc.

The exact number of participating FSPs is difficult to predict and will depend largely on the market's profitability. If the redispatch market proves attractive compared to other flexibility markets, it is likely that several FSPs will offer their services to asset owners, similar to the situation in balancing reserve markets. Increased participation generally fosters competition, potentially leading to lower prices and improved market liquidity. The presence of conventional power plants further supports initial liquidity in the market.

6. DSO perspective

Distribution networks were traditionally planned based on the estimated peak demand and annual demand increase, and by assuming concurrency factors below 100%. Using distributed flexibilities to provide ancillary services to the TSO was not considered in the planning of distribution networks. Consequently, the simultaneous activation of redispatch bids (whose providers are connected at the distribution level) may provoke much higher concurrency factors and thus violations of the operational distribution network limits. This issue can be addressed by conventional network reinforcement or by integrating the DSOs into the redispatch process.

Consequently, the DSO CBA should compare the costs of network reinforcements with the costs of establishing and operating a system that generates and communicates the data required by the bid set filter. To address the challenges of uncertain investment costs in the grid and control systems, unpredictable future redispatch demands

across various regions, and the limitation of using a fictional SimBench grid, the DSO Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) in this project adopts an alternative approach. The impact of distribution network reinforcement on the TSO's redispatch costs is evaluated as follows:

- The flexibility potential of industry (see D3.4) serves as a basis for potential RD bids from the industry located in the distribution network. The flexibility bids are assumed to be distributed equally. For the distribution network, a SimBench Model is used. This is because only limited field data is available and there are no critical grid situations at the moment. The grid is parametrized in a way so that problems can occur when too many bids are activated simultaneously. **This setup serves as the scenario with a non-reinforced grid.**
- **For the reinforced grid scenario**, the most critical bid combinations are assessed. Then the network reinforcement, which would be necessary to allow for full utilization of those bids (described in section 5.1) is carried out.
- The pareto fronts are calculated for the two scenarios. They show feasible bid combinations with the lowest costs for different amounts of energy (that could serve as potential redispatch bids). The study compares the results of the filtering process for the reinforced and original grid, using the partial large-scale analysis methodology described in D8.2. This comparison focuses on the quality of the identified Pareto fronts for both grids, taking into account both the costs and redispatch power of the identified bid combinations.

The following restrictions apply:

- Aggregation is not considered. Therefore, no minimum bid size is required, and no aggregation is simulated. The assumption is, that there are always other assets available to aggregate with to reach the minimum bid size.
- The load and production profiles need to be defined in a way, that critical grid situation occur by some grid combinations.
- For each timestep, the pareto front, which shows possible redispatch amounts to be activated (represented by different feasible bid sets) and their respective prices, is calculated.
- Due to the complex parametrization of the grid, the calculations have only been carried out for one day.

6.1. Grid reinforcement algorithm

In the original grid some bid combinations can cause voltage and/or current limit violations, to avoid those limit violations the grid gets reinforced. The reinforcement was performed with an automated grid reinforcement algorithm that detects limit violations and reinforces the grid to resolve them. A key concept of the algorithm is the **reinforcement schemas** of grid assets such as lines and transformers. These schemas provide information on the order in which a particular asset needs to be reinforced. Figure 9 provides an example for a reinforcement schema for a transformer in a secondary substation. When a current overload occurs in the transformer with the shown reinforcement schema, it will first be upgraded to the first entry in the schema which is a single transformer with a rated apparent power of 250 kVA. If this is insufficient to solve the overloading problem, the transformer gets reinforced to a single 400 kVA transformer. This process continues until the loading limit violation is resolved. The algorithm automatically skips steps in the schema that are unnecessary because they do not reduce the existing problem but rather increase it. For instance, if an existing transformer is overloaded with a rated apparent power of 500 kVA, replacing it with a 250 kVA transformer would not help to solve the problem. Instead, the algorithm starts with the first entry in the schema that exceeds the currently installed apparent power, which is 630 kVA.

Figure 9: Example for a reinforcement schema of a transformer in a secondary substation

The reinforcement is not performed for all possible bid combinations because this is computationally infeasible. Instead, critical bid combinations and times are filtered and selected. The algorithm iterates through all these critical

combinations and reinforces the grid whenever an overloading of a transformer or load, or an over or under voltage is identified. Furthermore, critical elements in the grid are identified as crucial for the n-1 security. If one of those critical elements is out of service, the grid must still be operated within its limits. Thus, the algorithm reinforces the lines and transformers for all critical bid combinations and critical elements being out of service to ensure that 1) no transformer is overloaded, 2) no line is overloaded, and 3) no terminal has over or under voltage. The following is a simplified pseudo-code for the reinforcement algorithm:

```
// Iterate over all critical bid combinations and times which have been identified
foreach bid_combination in selected_critical_bid_combinations do
  // Apply the load and generation for the critical bid combinations and
  // select the point in time for the critical bid combination
  apply(bid_combination)

  // To assure n-1 security, critical elements are identified
  foreach critical_element in selected_critical_grid_elements do
    // Change the critical element to be out of service
    out_of_service(critical_element)

    // Identify and reinforce all overloaded transformers until their
    // overloading is solved
    reinforce_overloaded_transformers()
    // Identify and reinforce all overloaded lines until their
    // overloading is solved
    reinforce_overloaded_lines()
    // Identify all terminals in the grid which have over or under voltage
    // Reinforce lines so solve the voltage problems
    reinforce_lines_for_overloaded_terminals()
  end
end
```

When applying the reinforcer to the test grid with the filtered critical bid combinations and critical elements, 18 lines with a system length of 16.6 km gets reinforced in the medium voltage grids. Additionally, one line in the high voltage grid with a system length of 0.2 km is reinforced. The costs for the grid reinforcement amount to 3.947 M€.

6.2. Results

This section presents the outcome of the cost-benefit analysis by comparing the initial grid setup with the reinforced grid. To do this, we re-conduct the partial large-scale analysis for the reinforced grid and compare it to the initial setup.

First, we examine the Pareto fronts identified through heuristic optimization for two selected timepoints, plotting them in their objective space. Second, we compare the minimum and maximum values found by the heuristic optimizer for both grid scenarios for all timepoints, both in absolute and relative terms. Finally, we consider all available bid combinations and take a closer look at the bid costs, evaluating how much they cost per MW.

6.2.1. Objective Space

Figure 3 shows the Pareto fronts identified by the heuristic optimizer for two selected timepoints: 9:15 and 15:15. The Pareto fronts for all timepoints are provided in Annex A. Positive power indicates a reduced active power flow from the transmission to the distribution network, while negative power indicates the opposite.

For the initial grid setup there are 42 bid combinations with redispatch powers between -38.2 and 89.3 MW and costs between -34 and 1.03 k€ are identified at 09:15 [Figure 3a]. For the reinforced grid setup there are 134 bid combinations with redispatch powers between -58.7 and 97.3 MW and costs between -60.35 and -17.25 k€ identified at 09:15 [Figure 3a]. The timepoint 9:15 was chosen because it exhibits the greatest disparity between the two minimum values. To better highlight the difference between these two minima, two horizontal lines were plotted at their respective minimum values. In the reinforced scenario, an extra -20.5 MW of flexibility can be provided compared to the initial scenario.

For the initial grid setup there are 62 bid combinations with redispatch powers between -48.9 and 83.4 MW and costs between -35.37 and -0.96 k€ identified at 15:15 [Figure 3b]. For the reinforced grid setup there are 101 bid combinations with redispatch powers between -50.6 and 94.8 MW and costs between -60.94 and -21.26 k€ identified at 15:15 [Figure 3b]. The timepoint 15:15 was selected due to its demonstration of the greatest disparity between the two maximum values. The two horizontal lines were plotted at their respective peak values for the two distinct scenarios. In the reinforced scenario, there's an additional 11.4 MW of flexibility available compared to the initial scenario.

Figure 3: Pareto fronts identified by heuristic optimization for all bids for the original grid (black markers) and the reinforced grid (grey markers). Two different time points are considered: (a) 09:15; (b) 15:15. Black and grey lines highlight the corresponding minimum and maximum.

Figure 4 illustrates the difference between the two maximum values in the positive y-direction, shown in black, and the difference between the two minimum values in the negative y-direction, shown in grey, for every 15-minute timepoint. The maximum value in the reinforced scenario is always higher than in the initial scenario, while the minimum value is consistently lower or equal for every timepoint. The graph illustrates the estimated RD power that can be gained by reinforcing the grid at any given time point throughout the day.

Figure 4: Estimated RD power gain over the course of a day in 15-minute resolution.

Figure 5 converts the data from Figure 4 into percentages. Figure 5 presents the estimated RD power gain as a percentage relative to the initial scenario, divided into positive values [Figure 5a] and negative values [Figure 5b].

Figure 5: Estimated RD power gain over the course of a day for the positive RD power (a) and the negative RD power (b) in percent with a 15-minute resolution.

6.2.2. Redispatch cost and power

Figure 6 displays all bid combinations identified by the heuristic optimizer throughout the day. A bid combination can be present at different time points. Therefore, it is possible for a bid combination to appear multiple times in this graph. Our aim is to determine the amount of RD power we can utilize in relation to its cost at a given timepoint, which requires retaining duplicate entries. In the case of the reinforced grid, the heuristic optimizer discovered 7693 bid combinations, compared to 3014 bid combinations without the reinforcement.

Figure 6: Cost and power of all redispatch bid combinations identified by the heuristic optimizer. At the estimated RD power of 25 MW, a cyan dotted line is drawn, and at 75 MW, a blue dotted line is drawn.

To compare the bid combinations in both scenarios, we examine intervals around the values at 25 MW and 75 MW, represented by horizontal lines. At these values, there are multiple bid combinations available in both scenarios. We are examining the interval from 74.5 to 75.5 MW and evaluate all bid combinations within this range for both scenarios. In the initial setup, there are 10 bid combinations ranging from 74.5 to 75.2 MW, with costs between -7.44 and -3.94 k€. In the reinforced grid scenario, there are 43 bid combinations ranging from 74.5 to 75.4 MW, with costs between -31.71 and -27.89 k€. To compare the bid combinations, we are looking at the price per MW. For the initial

setup, the costs range from -0.1 to -0.05 k€, with an average of -0.09 k€ per MW. For the reinforced grid setup, the costs range from -0.43 to -0.37 k€, with an average of -0.4 k€ per MW.

We are also looking at the interval ranging from 24.5 to 25.5 MW and evaluate all bid combinations for both grid scenarios. In the initial setup, there are 90 bid combinations ranging from 24.5 to 25.5 MW, with costs between -29.34 and -21.59 k€. In the reinforced grid scenario, there are 100 bid combinations ranging from 24.5 to 25.5 MW, with costs between -55.4 and -50.78 k€. To compare the bid combinations, we are looking at the price per MW. For the initial setup, the costs range from -1.17 to -0.85 k€, with an average of -1.03 k€ per MW. For the reinforced grid setup, the costs range from -2.25 to -2 k€, with an average of -2.1 k€ per MW.

7. Conclusion

This study assessed the integration of industrial assets into the Austrian redispatch process for the year 2030, evaluating both economic and operational effects through a detailed modelling framework and scenario-based CBA.

From the **transmission system operator's perspective**, incorporating industrial assets into the redispatch model leads to a reduction in total system costs of approximately 1—1.5% and a reduction in curtailed renewable electricity by up to 7.5%, with persistent curtailment reductions even under high participation markups. With at most around 250 MW as available industrial flexibility, the industry (without considering temporal simultaneity, etc.) is able to offer around 5% of the maximum peak requirements. While the integration of industrial assets leads to modest absolute cost reductions, their systemic value extends beyond immediate economic gains. In a future with significantly expanded renewable capacity and increasing grid congestion, industrial flexibility presents a viable lever for enhancing operational efficiency and minimizing renewable energy losses. However, unlocking the full potential of these assets may require regulatory adjustments, particularly concerning the remuneration of curtailed renewable generation.

Results indicate this curtailment of renewable generation to almost triple (from 57.4 GWh during 2024, cf. [1], to around 150 GWh), reflecting the planned expansion of renewable capacity by around 11 GW — an increase by more than a third of the currently installed capacities (around 25 GW). Within this context, the participation of industrial flexibility enables a reduction of curtailment by about 7.4 %, lowering the total to around 139~GWh. This reduction corresponds to roughly 20 % of the observed curtailed renewable energy in 2024 and underscores the substantial potential of industrial participation in facilitating more efficient domestic utilization of renewable electricity. Even if the savings remain modest in relative terms, the potential of industrial participation to contribute to overall system efficiency is made evident by that, which suggests that industrial flexibility might also play a significant role in reducing the need to curtail clean energy, thereby supporting broader decarbonization and energy system transition goals.

The impact of industrial assets is most notable on the provision of negative redispatch, effectively substituting curtailed renewable generation and enabling a more efficient use of domestic clean energy. While the overall contribution of industrial flexibility to redispatch volumes remains limited in absolute terms due to spatial and technical constraints, the targeted use of such assets can address specific structural limitations in the Austrian transmission network, especially in reducing reliance on conventional generation for negative redispatch. The sensitivity analysis also reveals that increasing industrial markups quickly erodes the economic benefits, underlining the importance of well-calibrated incentive structures. In the light of the overall macro situation, it is further interesting to observe that activations are increasingly triggered to counteract East-to-West (and North-to-South) flows, which aligns with empirically emerging trends but shows a clear shift to historic information that shows that costs were incurred by countering predominantly West-to-East flows.

In summary, integrating industrial flexibility into redispatch planning offers a feasible and beneficial pathway to improving decentralized support for congestion management, reducing system costs, and enabling higher renewable

integration. The design of market mechanisms or regulatory frameworks that allow for cost-efficient and reliable activation of industrial assets will be crucial for realizing this potential in practice.

The economic viability of **Flexibility Service Providers (FSPs)** of participating in the redispatch market heavily depends on specific market conditions. Markups in the range of €10–75/MWh may be sufficient under certain circumstances but are often inadequate—particularly for small-scale assets or manual operations. Therefore, including operational costs in the cost-based component of bids is considered essential. A major challenge lies in forecasting activation probabilities. Low or uncertain activation rates can significantly diminish the business case, reducing incentives for investment and participation. The relative attractiveness of the redispatch market is also influenced by competing flexibility markets, such as balancing services, where established business models already exist. Ultimately, the willingness of FSPs to engage will depend on the market's profitability, clarity of the regulatory framework, and alignment with existing operational strategies. For successful market implementation, transparent rules, fair remuneration schemes, and practical aggregation options are key.

The **DSO specific cost-benefit-analysis** revealed that the reinforced grid is beneficial because it provides more bid combinations, as no bid combinations are rejected due to grid limitations. Additionally, the reinforced grid increases the available redispatch power, but this improvement is not uniform across all timepoints, as shown in Figure 4. The most significant gains in estimated RD power occur during working hours, approximately from 6:00 to 16:00.

Comparing costs remains challenging, so we focused on two intervals and compared all bid combinations within them for both scenarios. We found that, on average, the bid combinations are approximately 25 k€ cheaper, and the combinations for the reinforced grid setup are closer together across all timepoints. However, comparing different estimated RD power and their costs is not very meaningful. This is because an increase in power leads to a reduction in unit cost, creating the counterintuitive effect that more RD power becomes cheaper. The overall result is that it is beneficial for the TSO if the DSO reinforces its grid.

As stated at the beginning, in a real-life scenario, the costs for grid expansion should be compared with the costs of operating the platform for redispatch at DSO level. In a round of discussions with network operators, it was noted that, in addition to the platform costs (see D8.3), it also requires additional personnel resources on DSO side equivalent to approximately 0.2 to 0.4 full-time equivalents.

We do not yet know how the final implementation of the TSO-DSO interaction process according to the Austrian market rules, will look like, nor which algorithm will ultimately be used for the optimization. However, based on our test network, we can make the following observations:

- Reinforcement of the distribution network enables greater flexibility potential at the distribution level to be utilized in the transmission network, potentially reducing redispatch costs.
- Each network must be assessed individually, improved monitoring supports more accurate evaluations for grid reinforcement.
- In addition to optimizing redispatch potential, there are many other factors that drive the need for grid reinforcement.

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